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Country of Origin Mediate Islamic Society's Belief in Purchasing Halal Products?

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Abstract:

This study examines the effect of the country of origin in explaining the relationship between the halal logo and marketing and the belief of Pontianak Muslims when receiving halal products from Malaysia. The study used primary data collected by distributing questionnaires to respondents determined by purposive sampling. The research sample was all Muslim communities in the city of Pontianak, West Kalimantan. This study uses path analysis with SPSS tools to answer the research hypothesis. The results showed that the Country of Origin variable could not mediate the relationship between the Halal Logo variable and the Confidence Choice variable. In contrast, it could mediate the relationship between the Marketing Variable and the Confidence Choice variable.

Keywords: Confidence Choice, Country of Origin, Halal Products, Marketing.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Muslim population, which reaches 23% (approximately 1.8 billion) of the total world population, is an issue that cannot be ignored by the industry today. With an average growth rate of 3 percent per year, this population will reach 26% (2.2 billion) of the total world population in 2030 (Kamila, 2020). Most of these Muslim communities live in South Asia and the Asia Pacific, particularly in Indonesia, Pakistan, India, and Bangladesh, estimated to reach 1.3 billion by 2030. This significant Muslim population represents a potential market share for halal food products (Hayat, 2012).

Halal food products are a profitable market arena. The influence of halal food is quite significant in the world food industry, reaching nearly USD 667 million (approximately 20%) of the entire global food industry. It is likely that, along with the increasing number of Muslim populations and the incomes of halal consumers, and the demand for food that reaches more than 70% by 2050, the need for halal food will also increase (Sukoso et al., 2020). Thus, a marketing strategy that can meet the wishes of the Muslim community requires (Fithriana and Kusuma, 2018).

Marketing of halal products requires a comprehensive marketing strategy by paying attention to the behavior of Muslim consumers that nowadays are becoming aware of the halalness issue of a product. The marketing strategy must be adequate, following the company's objectives, controlling, and describing the current business opportunities. In addition, situation analysis, determining the ideal type of customer, marketing targets, appropriate marketing tools, and a budget that supports marketing also need to be considered (Kotler, 2016). In the context of marketing halal products, labeling products with halal logos is a significant issue. Several studies conducted using samples from Russia and China show that the halal logo influences buying a halal product (Hong et al., 2019; Shamakov and Asnawi, 2020). In addition, country of origin is one factor considered by consumers when determining a product (Piron, 2000; Aichner, 2014; Adina, Gabriela, and Roxana-Denisa, 2015; Yunus and Rashid, 2016; Wegapitiya and Dissanayake, 2018). In the context of halal products, consumer confidence in the country of origin is an essential factor (Aziz and Chok, 2013; Rios, Riquelme and Abdelaziz, 2014; Borzooei and Asgari, 2015; Alfikri, Baga and Suprehatin, 2019; Fahmi et al., 2019; Teng, Abdullah and Heng, 2019; Harahap, Nasution and Tarigan, 2020). By using the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), Alam and Sayuti (2011); Shamakov and Asnawi (2020) examine consumer behavior when buying a halal product. The study results show that the behavior of Muslims represented by attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control affects the purchase of halal products in Malaysia. However, Alam and Sayuti's (2011) research did not include the Country of Origin element when explaining this relationship. Therefore, this study focuses on Country of Origin in explaining consumer behavior when receiving halal products in the perspective of attribution theory introduced by Heider (1958) and TPB presented by Ajzen (1967).

Amid the variability findings of studies accompanied with the latest business phenomena regarding halal products, the authors have the motivation to conduct in-depth research of the halalness issue by focusing on examining consumer choices for a halal product. Remarkably, this study is intended to explore the relationship between marketing strategy and halal logo with the beliefs of Pontianak Muslims in receiving halal products from Malaysia through the Country of Origin as a mediating variable. This research contributes and expands our understanding of consumer behavior in buying halal products, especially in the Pontianak area.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This study uses attribution theory (Heider, 1958) and the Theory of Planned Behavior/TPB (Ajzen, 1967) to explain the relationship between belief and marketing strategy and halal logo through a country of origin. Attribution theory explains how internal factors such as character, attitude, nature, and external factors such as the pressure of certain situations or circumstances that influence individual behavior influence an individual's behavior towards himself or others (Wijethilake, Munir and Appuhami, 2017). At the same time, the main focus of the TPB is the individual's intention to behave in a certain way. Through preferences, one can observe suggestions that motivate a person to conduct particular behavior. In other words, the intention is a sign of how hard people are willing to try and how much effort or effort the individual puts out to imply an attitude or behavior.

Several variables determine the trust of consumers to choose and buy a product. For this reason, it is vital to conduct an intense study to determine the intended variable. The study results can provide a particular contribution for producers to manage their business; thus, consumers can accept and use their products as reference products. A number of psychological dimensions such as motivation, perception, learning, and attitude need to be considered to increase consumer confidence in the product (Kotler, 2016). In the perspective of halal products, innovative marketing aspects, which consider the psychological factors of target consumers, need to be carried out. The concept of Islamic marketing based on religious marketing, namely marketing guided within the framework of Islamic Sharia (Alserhan, 2011), can increase the confidence of Muslim consumers to buy halal products. Confidence to buy halal products will be more substantial if the halal logo is embedded in the packaging of halal products.

The general perception of a country can underlie the image of the Country of Origin, especially regarding the quality of the products produced by that country (Genç and Gül Bayraktaroğlu, 2017). The product is a representation of the specific characteristics of a nation. For example, a country has an image related to mechanical engineering, design, or quality worth selling. Consumers of a product from abroad will usually be careful about these aspects, especially if the consumer has little knowledge of the intended

outcome.

Country of Origin helps reduce stereotypes or consumer prejudice on foreign products, namely, by investigating the source, content of the product so that consumers can conclude the quality of a product. Consumers will grow their confidence in foreign products through the image of this country of origin if they lack knowledge or information about a product. When consumers consider the country of origin aspect, they will focus on its creation. Furthermore, if consumers do not know the actual producer country, they will usually depend on the brand's source (Listiana, 2012).

Several factors underlie Muslim consumer confidence in halal products. For example, hygiene, health, and product content guarantees are processed according to the Islamic code of ethics. In practice, these factors do not only apply to Muslim consumers. Non-Muslim communities also apply this principle when they buy certain products. Therefore, the increasing market demand for halal products is contributed by Muslims and all consumers from various groups regardless of religious attributes.

This assumption underlies this research. Specifically, this study is intended to determine the factors that influence consumers' confidence choice in consuming. These factors are Country of Origin, which is used as a mediating variable between the input variables (Halal Logo and Marketing) and the output variable (Confidence Choice). The following is the conceptual framework of this research:

Figure 1. Research's Framework

Halal certification is a systematic testing process to ascertain the halalness of a commodity manufactured by a company. Even though an item has been labeled with a halal logo, stereotyped consumer attitudes towards foreign products originating from abroad can affect their level of trust to consume the product. Country of origin can aid in lessening consumer stereotypes about the product. The working mechanism of the country of origin is to investigate the source and other content of the intended outcome so that consumers can conclude the quality of a product. The image of the country of origin can foster consumer confidence in a product if consumers are less informed regarding the product. In this regard, consumers probably have no information about the country that produces a product, and they only know the origin of the brand of the product (Listiana, 2012).

Country of origin (COO) can affect three processes: cognitive processes established by consumer discernments of the COO image, affective processes established by feelings on the country, and normative processes established by intentions and performance (Genç and Gül Bayraktaroğlu, 2017). Furthermore, consumers will usually respond to an item based on its relationship to the social norms and values (Brijs, Bloemer, and Kasper, 2011). The normative process involves cognitive and affective responses when determining the product to be consumed.

Products sealed with the halal logo mean that the product's halal quality has been verified. In addition, reducing consumer stereotype attitudes towards products originating from a country through the country of origin will also increase consumer confidence in consuming these halal products. This result supports the research done by Rios, Riquelme, and Abdelaziz (2014), which states that consumers in Kuwait are more confident to consume local/domestic products and products produced by other Muslim countries than those produced by non-Muslim nations. Thus, this study builds hypothesis as follows:

H₁: Halal logo affects confidence choice of halal products through the country of origin

"Halalaan Thoyyiban" is Islamic sharia that underlies the concept of marketing a product. This concept states that the products and services sold must not contravene Islamic law and do not comprise items that are banned by faith. For example, it includes elements of usury in financial products (Fahmi et al., 2019). Meanwhile, the socio-economic underlying a country will cause differences in characteristics between countries. Consumers will pay attention to the image of these countries when they decide to buy a product (Fruchter, Jaffe, and Nebenzahl, 2006).

One of the elements in marketing halal products is through promotions under Islamic law, which does not contain prohibited things such as pornography. Such an image will increase consumer confidence when choosing halal products. The combination of good marketing and country of origin will increase consumer confidence. This opinion is in line with research conducted by Rahim (2016), which found that countries in East Asia have a higher perception of halal products compared to similar perceptions in Middle Eastern countries. It is assumed that although consumers in the East Asia region are lack information about how to produce commodities, they have high knowledge about halal products. Through the discernment of country of origin, consumers have conviction in eating halal foods from a nation. This condition triggers the high growth of the halal market in a particular country. To that end, the hypotheses developed in the study are as follows:

H₂: Marketing affects the confidence choice of halal products through the country of origin

The specific socio-economic characteristics can form a particular image, such as power-driven manufacturing, strategy, and feature that are worth selling for consumers (Fruchter, Jaffe, and Nebenzahl, 2006). Consumers will usually be careful of a new product from abroad, especially from countries with a particular image. Consumers who have little knowledge about specific products will usually refer to the country of origin, which is a conception built from a typical awareness of commodities' features manufactured by a nation (Genç and Gül Bayraktaroğlu, 2017). In other words, country of origin can help reduce stereotyping or prejudice against products by investigating the source, content/composition of the product so that consumers can conclude the quality of a product (Barbarossa et al., 2016).

Country of origin, usually measured by a good image of a country, will also foster consumer confidence about a product when they have less knowledge or information about the product (Yunus and Rashid, 2016). Chao and Rajendran (1993) found that country of origin has a significant effect on consumer decisions to consume a commodity in addition to halal certification. For example, respondents are more pleased to possess pieces of stuff from Japan than pieces of stuff from Germany. They assume that Japan has an image of product quality superior to Germany's image of product quality. This finding is in line with the study of Fruchter, Jaffe, and Nebenzahl (2006), which state that a country has a good representation from some facets such as power-driven manufacturing, strategy, and feature that is worth selling. To that end, the hypotheses developed in the study are as follows:

H₃: Country of origin affects the confidence choice of halal products

3. METHODS

The study assumed that ontologically, the reality is objective and can be separately investigated and controlled. Thus, it is positivist research. Moreover, from the view of problem characteristics, this research aims to test hypotheses or answer questions related to the current status of the subjects studied.

This study uses primary data collecting through a questionnaire technique and measures using a Likert scale. The Likert scale is relevant to this study as the method measures attitudes by stating their agreement or disagreement with particular subjects, objects, or events. The Likert scale is generally determined using six rating points, namely: (1) none, (2) very low, (3) low, (4) high, (5) very high, and (6) surely.

The population is the Muslim community in the Pontianak City, West Kalimantan. The samples were all men and women chosen by purposive sampling, based on specific criteria, namely:

1. Respondents are all Muslim communities in Pontianak, West Kalimantan.
2. Respondents have education from high school (SMA) to graduate level.
3. The type of work and income does not limit respondents. The number of samples in this study was 500 samples. Determination of the sample size in the survey method research using the Lemeshow formula, with the unknown population size (N) or $(N-n)/(N-1)=1$ then the sample size is calculated using the

following formula

$$n = \frac{Z^2 \alpha \cdot p(1-p)}{d^2}$$

where:

- n = minimum number of samples required
- Z² = degree of significance
- p = population
- d = limit of error or absolute precision

The variables used in this study consisted of the dependent (Confidence Choice), independent (Halal Logo and Marketing) and mediation (Country of Origin) variables. Table 1 presents the operational definition of each research variable measured using question items and measured using a six-point Likert scale.

Table 1. Definition of Research Variable

Variable	Definition	Indicators
Halal Logo	A label is any information regarding food in the form of pictures, writings, a combination of both, or other conditions attached to food, inserted into, affixed to, or is part of food packaging. (PP No. 69/1999 on halal labeling)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Understand in choosing products with the halal logo 2. Understand how to get a halal logo legally 3. Knowing halal products that come from abroad 4. Knowing the fake logo 5. Recognize the difference between real and fake logos
Marketing	Marketing is the totality of business activities aimed at planning, pricing, promoting, and distributing goods and services that satisfy the needs of both existing and potential buyers.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Trust very high-quality halal products. 2. The manufacture of local halal products has the same quality 3. Prices of halal products tend to be higher 4. The promotion of halal products increases sales 5. Place selection can lead to a lack of buyers 6. It is more convincing if the producer is a Muslim
Country of Origin	Consumer perceptions of products from the country of origin are both related to positive and negative images that can influence the decision to buy	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Want to buy products with the halal logo from your own country as well as from foreign countries 2. Prefer the MUI halal logo from their own country 3. Pay more for products with your own country's halal logo 4. Buy without considering the country and institution that issued the halal certificate
Confidence	Trust is divided into self-confidence and purchase trust. Self-confidence is connected to the aptitude of confidence that a person has in social situations, while purchase confidence is knowledge of a product that shows how a consumer is able and assured concerning market choices and performance.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Confidence to buy halal products 2. Interested in buying halal products 3. Recommending halal products to others 4. Providing halal products to families 5. Giving halal products to friends

Before testing the hypothesis, we conducted data validity through Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) to measure the validity of the questionnaire. The validity of the correlation between variables is seen based on the size of the Kaiser Meyer Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy (KMO MSA) and the significance coefficient of Bartlett's Test of Sphericity. If the KMO MSA coefficient is more than 0.50, then the data validity is acceptable and vice versa if the coefficient is less than 0.50. At the same time, Bartlett's Test of Sphericity is measured from a significance coefficient of less than 5% or 0.05 (Hair, Hollingsworth, Randolph, & Chong, 2017). Furthermore, the reliability test was carried out to determine how much the variable can be trusted (Manuaba & Gayatri, 2017), namely if it has a Cronbach's Alpha value of more than 0.6 (Ghozali, 2016).

Several tests, such as normality, multicollinearity, and heteroscedasticity tests, were carried out to produce a good regression model. The normality test of the data was carried out by looking at the Kolmogorov-Smirnov value, which was greater than 0.05. Multicollinearity test is seen from the amount of VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) and tolerance. So a low tolerance value is the same as a high VIF value (because VIF = 1/tolerance). The cut-off value that is commonly used to indicate multicollinearity is the tolerance value 0.01 or equal to the VIF value 10. Moreover, the heteroscedasticity test is detected through the Plot Graph between the predicted value of the dependent variable, namely ZPRED and residual SRESID.

If there is a specific pattern, it indicates that heteroscedasticity has occurred. If there is no clear pattern and the points spread above and below the number 0 on the Y axis, there is no heteroscedasticity.

This study employs path analysis to test the effect of the intervening variable. Path analysis extends multiple linear regression analysis to estimate causality between predetermined variables based on theory. It allows the researcher to evaluate the direct and indirect effect of the relationship between variables through the path coefficient, namely the standardized regression coefficient, which is calculated through two structural equations to test the hypothesis.

In this study, the direct and indirect effects of the halal logo (VHL) and marketing (VM) variables can be seen as follows:

- Direct effect : VHL → VCC
- : VM → VCC
- Indirect effect : VHL → VCoC → VCC
- : VM → VCoC → VCC

Next, a mathematical equation that incorporates all the hypothesized variables is constructed as follows:

$$VCC = \alpha + \delta_1 VHL + \delta_1 VM + \delta_1 VCoC + \varepsilon$$

where:

- VCC = Variable of Confidence Choice
- VHL = Variable of Halal Logo
- VM = Variable of Marketing
- VCoC = Variable of Country of Origin
- δ = Regression coefficient
- α = Constant
- ε = Variance

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Before testing the hypothesis, the researcher(s) did the data validity and reliability tests and a series of classical assumption tests. The results of the data validity test were presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Validity Test

Variable	Questionnaire item	Significance	Limitation value	Conclusion
Variable of Halal Logo	VHL_1-12	0,00	0,00	Valid
Variable of Marketing	VM_1-11	0,00	0,00	Valid
Variable of Country of Origin	VCoC_1-12	0,00	0,00	Valid
Variable of Confidence Choice	VCC_1-9	0,00	0,00	Valid

Source: Processed Primary Data (2020)

Table 2 shows the number of questionnaire items for each research variable. The validity test results indicate that all statement items in each variable have a significance value below 0.05 which is the limit value of an acceptable research questionnaire item. Thus, the questionnaire items for all variables are valid and can be used to measure the variables studied.

Meanwhile, the reliability test results show that Cronbach's Alpha value is greater than 0.700 (See Table 3). The data used in this study is reliable; thus, the following subsequent analysis can be conducted.

Table 3. Reliability Test

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha
Variable of Halal Logo	0,862
Variable of Marketing	0,774
Variable of Country of Origin	0,790
Variable of Confidence Choice	0,745

Source: Processed Primary Data (2020)

To produce a BLUE hypothesis test, a series of classical assumption tests were carried out. The results of the normality test of the data through the histogram graph have shown a regular distribution pattern because the points spread around the diagonal line, and the distribution follows the direction of the diagonal line. Meanwhile, the test output shows that all independent variables have a tolerance value or a tolerance value of more than 0.1 and a VIF of less than 10. It indicates no multicollinearity between the independent variables so that the data is applicable to use in research.

Furthermore, hypothesis testing using path analysis through SPSS 23 software was carried out. In this study, path analysis is used to estimate quantitatively the relationship between Halal Logo and Marketing and Confidence Choice mediated by Country of Origin. The path analysis test results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Path Analysis Results

Variable	Coefficient	t-Test	Significance
Constant		1,745	0,082
VHL	0,168	5,391	0,000
VM	0,153	3,888	0,000
VCoC	0,356	9,062	0,000

Source: Processed Primary Data (2020)

Based on the results presented in Table 4, a structural equation or structural model can be constructed as follows:

$$VCC = \alpha + \delta_1 VHL + \delta_2 VM + \delta_3 VCoC + \varepsilon$$

where:

- VCC = Variable of Confidence Choice
- VHL = Variable of Halal Logo
- VM = Variable of Marketing
- VCoC = Variable of Country of Origin
- δ = Regression coefficient
- α = Constant
- ε = Variance

The analysis produces a path diagram, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 2. A Path Analysis Diagram (2020)

Based on the coefficient values presented in Figure 2, it can be seen that the magnitude of the direct or indirect influence between the hypothesized variables is:

- VHL Value → VCoC is 0,074
- VM Value → CoC is 0,399
- VcoV Value → VCC is 0,356
- VHL Value → VCC is 0,168
- VM Value → VCC is 0,153

The effect received by an endogenous variable from two exogenous variables can be observed separately or

together. The influence individually can directly or indirectly influence other exogenous variables that act as mediating variables. Suppose the result of the indirect effect is greater than the direct effect. In that case, it can be concluded that the actual relationship is an indirect relationship or a mediating variable and vice versa. The impact of exogenous variables on endogenous variables can be calculated as follows:

Indirect effect analysis:

- a. Halal Logo effect on Confidence Choice

$$\text{Direct effect (VHL, VCC)} = 0,168$$

Indirect effect through VCoC

$$\text{VHL} * \text{VCoC} = 0,074 * 0,7622 = 0.0564$$

The analysis results show that the direct effect is more significant than the indirect result (0.168 > 0.0564). Based on these results, it can be concluded that structural ties directly affect Confidence Choice.

- b. Marketing effect on Confidence Choice

$$\text{Direct effect (VM, VCC)} = 0,153$$

Indirect effect through VCoC

$$\text{VM} * \text{VCoC} = 0,399 * 0,6655 = 0.2655$$

The analysis results show that the indirect impact is more significant than the direct result (0.26655 > 0.153). Based on these results, it can be concluded that structural ties indirectly affect Confidence Choice.

Based on the indirect effect analysis results, the total effect of each independent variable can be calculated, namely the Halal Logo Variable (VHL) and the Marketing Variable (VM).

- a. Total effect of Halal Logo on Confidence Choice:

$$0,168 + 0,0564 = 0.2244 \text{ (22,44\%)}$$

- b. Total effect of Marketing on Confidence Choice:

$$0,153 + 0,2655 = 0,4185 \text{ (41,85\%)}$$

Thus, it can be concluded that the influence of other variables outside the structural equations built in the study is $100 - R\text{square} = 100 - 55.7 = 44.3\%$. Table 5 presents the summary results of the path analysis.

Table 5. Summary of Hypothesis Test

Remarks	Variable of Halal Logo	Variable of Marketing
Direct effect	0,168	0,153
Indirect effect	0,0564	0,2655
Total effects	0,2244	0,4185
Criteria	Direct < Indirect	Direct > Indirect
Significance	0,0000	0,0000
Conclusion	Country of Origin as mediating variable	Country of Origin as mediating variable

Source: Processed Primary Data (2020)

Effect of Halal Logo on Confidence Choice through Country of Origin

Statistical tests notify that Halal Logo affects Confidence Choice, but Country of Origin does not succeed as a mediating variable. These results support research conducted by (Borzooei and Asgari, 2015) which states that consumer decisions to choose halal products are determined by taste, price, and packaging but contradict the results of studies (Piron, 2000; Rios, Riquelme and Abdelaziz, 2014). The findings of this study indicate that the region is not the main reason for consumers to choose products, but they are more concerned with the halalness of the product, where this finding is supported by studies Aziz and Chok (2013). The reason is consumers have less familiar with the product. Through the Theory of Planned Behavior, Alam and Sayuti (2011) explain that the Halal Logo is the main factor that underlies people's belief in halal products.

Effect of Marketing on Confidence through Country of Origin

Statistical tests notify that Marketing has a positive and significant effect on Confidence Choice, and Country of Origin has succeeded in becoming a mediating variable. This result indicates that the marketing carried out has succeeded in providing knowledge to consumers about a product, even though the product

comes from abroad. Country of origin can help reduce stereotyping or prejudice against products (Barbarossa et al., 2016) by investigating the source, content, and others about the product so that consumers can conclude the merchandise' value (Hong & Wyer, 1989). Consumers with insufficient acquainted with a product incline to custom the appearance of the country of origin in mounting their confidence concerning it (Wegapitiya and Dissanayake, 2018; Dursun et al., 2019).

Based on the attribution theory, consumer perceptions by marketing can make people feel confident to buy a halal product (Hunt and Hartman, 2015) without a Country of Origin image. There is a good strategy in the marketing process because it broadly covers the 4Ps, namely Product, Price, Promotion, and Place, which make people sure to buy halal products.

Effect of Country of Origin on Confidence Choice

Statistical tests notify that the Country of Origin has a positive and significant effect on Confidence Choice, which means that the more convincing the origin of the product from a country, the higher the Confidence Choice. Country of origin can help reduce stereotyping or prejudice against products by conducting source investigations so that consumers can conclude the quality of a product (Rios, Riquelme, and Abdelaziz, 2014). Consumers with insufficient acquainted with a product incline to custom the appearance of the country of origin in mounting their confidence concerning it. The country of origin of the product is a significant aspect of the country of origin that consumers consider when choosing a product.

Kanitra and Kusumawati (2018) found that the Country of Origin has a positive and significant effect on Confidence Choice because the country of origin labeled as Islamic has a majority of Muslims. Consumers believe that the country of origin that manufactures the product and distributes it mainly to Indonesia will affect the Confidence Choice in buying halal products. They think that the Country of Origin, especially Islamic countries and countries where the majority are Muslims, have felt that they have stages in determining halal products to believe in these products.

5. CONCLUSION

This study examines the effect of country of origin in explaining the relationship between Halal Logo and Marketing variables and the beliefs of Pontianak Muslims when accepting halal products from Malaysia. The study results found that the Country of Origin variable could not mediate the relationship between the Halal Logo variable and the Confidence Choice variable. In contrast, it could mediate the relationship between the Marketing variable and the Confidence Choice variable.

This study only considers the halal logo and marketing factors as independent variables and country of origin as a mediating variable in explaining beliefs in perceiving halal products. The results show that these variables can only describe the existing relationship by 55.2%, and the remaining 44.8% is influenced by other variables outside the model built in this study.

6. RECOMMENDATION

For further researchers to insert independent variables that theoretically can affect confidence. In addition, as we analyze the survey based on each respondent's perception of the research instrument items, it allows bias or miss perception. Future research can expand the object and area of study.

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